

DEVELOPMENT OF A ML-DRIVEN SELF-OPTIMIZATION WORKFLOW FOR THE PRODUCTION OF NITROGEN-RICH COMPOUNDS IN CONTINUOUS PROCESSING

Gonzalo Araya Vargas, Dusan Boskovic, Maud Schwarzer, Alexander Mendl
Fraunhofer Institute for Chemical Technology ICT, Pfinztal, Germany

Abstract: We report the development of an autonomous self-optimization platform for continuous flow chemistry, integrating microreactor technology, automation, inline FT-IR analytics, and Bayesian optimization. The platform enables data-driven exploration and optimization of chemical reactions with minimal human intervention. As a case study, we applied this workflow to the synthesis of diazoacetonitrile, a reactive intermediate of interest for diverse applications.

Three experimental campaigns were conducted: (i) reproducing literature-reported conditions to validate system reliability, (ii) exploring higher-dimensional design spaces by increasing the number of process variables, and (iii) expanding the search beyond previous operating boundaries. Across all campaigns, the platform demonstrated robust, reproducible performance, completing over 70 autonomous experiments in less than 20 hours.

The results underscore the platform's flexibility and efficiency in optimizing complex reactions. Its modular design makes it broadly applicable to a wide range of continuous processes in synthetic chemistry, including those involving hazardous or sensitive transformations.

1. Introduction

Energetic materials, such as explosives, propellants, and pyrotechnics, are vital to a wide range of industrial and defense applications. Central to their development is the synthesis of nitrogen-rich compounds, which often exhibit high enthalpies of formation and favorable detonation properties [1]. However, the synthesis of such compounds is inherently hazardous due to their reactivity and sensitivity, requiring stringent control of reaction parameters to ensure both safety and efficiency.

Traditionally, these compounds have been synthesized using batch processes. While batch chemistry remains a common approach in early-stage research and development, it presents several limitations when dealing with hazardous or fast reactions. Poor heat and mass transfer, inconsistent mixing, and the lack of real-time monitoring make batch methods suboptimal for reactions requiring precise control. Moreover, process scale-up can be non-trivial and poses additional safety concerns.

Continuous flow chemistry offers a promising alternative. Microreactor-based systems, in particular, enable excellent control over reaction conditions due to enhanced heat and mass transfer, small reactor volumes, and inherently safer process configurations. These systems also lend themselves well to automation and inline analytics, making them ideal platforms for intelligent reaction optimization [2].

Despite these advantages, the optimization of continuous reactions remains a resource-intensive task when relying on traditional strategies such as One Factor at a Time (OFAT) or Design of Experiments (DoE). These methods require a large number of experiments to map multidimensional parameter spaces and often fail to exploit the full potential of automation.

To address these challenges, we are developing a machine learning-driven self-optimization platform that integrates continuous flow chemistry, inline Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy, and Bayesian optimization (BO). This autonomous workflow is applied to the synthesis of diazoacetone nitrile — a reactive intermediate relevant to the synthesis of nitrogen-rich compounds.

Bayesian optimization is a data-efficient global optimization strategy particularly well suited for problems where evaluations are expensive or time-consuming [3]. BO constructs a probabilistic surrogate model of the objective function, typically using a Gaussian Process, and employs an acquisition function to balance exploration of unknown regions with exploitation of promising areas. The surrogate model is updated after each new experiment, progressively improving its predictive accuracy. To initialize the process, a small set of experiments is performed at the beginning to generate the first training data for the model. This iterative and adaptive approach enables the identification of optimal experimental conditions with a minimal number of iterations, significantly accelerating the optimization of chemical processes [4].

The diazotization of aminoacetonitrile hydrochloride, presented in Figure 1, was selected to test the platform due to its relevance and the challenges associated with safe handling. The transformation proceeds under biphasic conditions (water/dichloromethane) using sodium nitrite as the diazotizing agent [5].

Figure 1: Diazotization of aminoacetonitrile hydrochloride (1) with sodium nitrite (2) to form diazoacetone nitrile (3) under biphasic conditions ($\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{DCM}$).

In this study, we present the architecture of the self-optimization platform, describe the experimental setup, and share preliminary results demonstrating the potential of the approach for

accelerating the development of complex synthetic routes in flow.

2. Materials and Methods

The equipment necessary to construct the autonomous platform includes four syringe pumps (2 × HiTec Zang, SyrDos; 2 × Sykam, S1610), one peristaltic pump (Vapourtec SF-10) a water bath (Ministat 125, Huber), a microreactor (Little Thing Factory, ST Design), a membrane separation module (Zaiput, SEP-10), a back pressure regulator (Equilibar), a pressure controller, and sensors for pressure and temperature. For inline analytics, a MATRIX-MF FT-IR spectrometer (Bruker) is used. A schematic of the platform setup is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Schematic of the autonomous self-optimization platform integrating continuous flow synthesis, pressure control, inline FT-IR analytics, and automated feedback control.

In the schematic, a 2M aqueous solution of aminoacetonitrile (AAN HCl, 98+; Thermo Scientific) is mixed with a 2.4 M aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (p.s.; Sigma-Aldrich) using a T-mixer. The resulting reaction mixture enters the microreactor, where it is combined with dichloromethane to extract the formed diazoacetonitrile. System pressure is maintained using a back pressure regulator (BPR), which is automatically adjusted via a pressure controller. After the BPR, the flow enters a phase separation unit. This device separates the aqueous and organic phases:

the organic phase containing the product passes through a hydrophobic membrane, while the aqueous phase and evolved gases continue through the main outlet. Phase separation is critical, as the presence of water or gas bubbles in the FT-IR measurement cell can interfere with spectral quality and compromise the optimization process.

Finally, the organic phase enters the FT-IR flow cell, where spectra are collected in real time. The formation of diazoacetonitrile (DAN) is monitored by integrating the IR absorption between 2125 and 2070 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the N=N asymmetric stretching vibration of the diazo group.

These spectral data are passed to a Bayesian optimization algorithm, which autonomously determines the next experimental conditions to evaluate. The algorithm then communicates with the automation software (LabVision) to adjust the relevant experimental parameters accordingly.

An automated cleaning system for the optical probe was also integrated into the platform. This feature is crucial to mitigate fouling caused by residual amounts of water passing through the membrane separation module. The cleaning process is automatically triggered when the presence of water in the collected spectra exceeds a predefined threshold. Spectral monitoring for water signals is performed continuously during the experiments, ensuring consistent measurement quality and minimizing manual intervention.

3. Results and Discussion

To evaluate the performance and adaptability of the autonomous optimization platform, three experimental campaigns were conducted. Each campaign escalated in complexity — from validation against existing literature, to increasing variable dimensionality, and finally to exploring novel experimental regions.

3.1 Experiment 1 – Reproducibility Study

The first experiment focused on validating the reproducibility of the self-optimization platform by exploring the same parameter space described in previous literature [5]. The optimization targeted three variables: temperature (35–70°C), residence time (52–210 s), and pressure (2–6 bar). A total of 15 experiments were performed in under 4 hours.

As seen in Figure 3a, the system rapidly converged to high-yield conditions. The parallel coordinate plot (Figure 3b) confirms that regions with moderate residence times and elevated temperatures yielded the highest DAN concentrations. The Bayesian optimization algorithm effectively balanced exploration and exploitation, selecting informative experiments and avoiding redundant trials. The results matched well with the published results, validating the platform's accuracy and stability.

(a) Peak area (2125–2070 cm^{-1}) of DAN across experiments.

(b) Parallel coordinates showing variable combinations and measured outcomes.

Figure 3: Experiment 1 – Reproducibility of published results using the autonomous platform.

3.2 Experiment 2 – Increased Complexity with a Fourth Variable

In the second experiment, a fourth variable — extra acid concentration (0.2–0.4 M) — was introduced to investigate the platform’s capacity to handle increased dimensionality. A total of 28 experiments were completed in 7 hours.

(a) Yield progression during optimization with four variables.

(b) Parallel coordinates illustrating the influence of acid concentration.

Figure 4: Experiment 2 – Optimization under increased complexity with four variables.

The addition of extra acid positively impacted DAN yield, as shown by the increasing trend in Figure 4a. Interestingly, the optimal temperature shifted compared to Experiment 1: while higher temperatures favored the reaction initially, in the presence of additional acid, lower temperatures

led to better outcomes. This behavior can be rationalized by the dual role of acid in the diazotization reaction. Increased proton concentration enhances the formation of nitrosating species such as nitrous acid (HNO_2), promoting efficient conversion of aminoacetonitrile to diazoacetonitrile. However, given the inherent thermal instability of diazoacetonitrile, higher temperatures simultaneously accelerate its decomposition. In the acid-enriched system, where formation is already facilitated, operating at lower temperatures helps preserve the diazo product and maximize yield.

3.3 Experiment 3 – Exploration Outside the Initial Boundaries

The third experiment was designed to explore new regions of the parameter space not previously examined in the literature. The temperature range was extended to include lower values (25–70°C) and the residence time down to 20 s. A total of 30 experiments were autonomously executed over 8 hours.

(a) Yield progression showing discovery of new optima.

(b) Parallel plot revealing optimal zones at mild conditions.

Figure 5: Experiment 3 – Expanded design space reveals new optimal regions.

As shown in Figure 5a, the platform was able to improve yield beyond what was observed in earlier campaigns. Notably, Figure 5b indicates that the highest yields were obtained at mild temperatures and short residence times. This experiment underscores the importance of allowing algorithms to explore outside conventionally defined design spaces to uncover superior operating conditions.

Collectively, these experiments demonstrate the robustness and versatility of the self-optimizing platform. From validating literature data to uncovering previously unknown optima, the system consistently delivered efficient, reproducible, and data-driven optimization cycles with full automation and inline analytics.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we presented the development and application of an autonomous self-optimization platform for the continuous synthesis of fine and potentially hazardous chemical compounds. The system integrates microreactor technology, inline FT-IR analytics, automation software, and a Bayesian optimization algorithm to enable fully data-driven reaction optimization.

Through three experimental campaigns, the platform demonstrated:

- High reproducibility when replicating literature-reported conditions, validating both the analytical strategy and system control.
- The capability to handle increased process complexity with the introduction of a fourth variable, yielding valuable mechanistic insights.
- The ability to explore expanded parameter spaces, identifying superior operating conditions beyond conventionally defined limits.

Across all campaigns, the system operated continuously and autonomously, executing over 70 experiments with minimal human intervention. The use of inline analytics and real-time decision-making significantly reduced the time and resources required for optimization, while ensuring reproducibility, safety, and robustness.

Although this work focused on the synthesis of diazoacetonitrile as a case study, the modular nature of the platform makes it easily adaptable to a wide variety of continuous flow reactions. This includes those involving energetic materials, pharmaceutical intermediates, or fine chemicals requiring precise process control.

These findings highlight the potential of combining flow chemistry, machine learning, and automation to accelerate the development and optimization of complex chemical processes. Future work will focus on extending the platform to additional chemistries and incorporating multi-objective optimization to simultaneously optimize yield, safety, and sustainability metrics.

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